

Climate and energy scenario and projection comparison. Draft workflow & typology

Working paper

Hannah Förster¹, Mirjam Stappel², Lukas Emele¹, Anne Siemons¹, Christian Winger¹

Keywords: scenario comparison, projection comparison, typology, projections, climate, energy, energy systems modelling, Open Energy Platform, Open Energy Ontology

1 Introduction

In climate and energy modelling, scenario projections of specific variables of interest (for example greenhouse gas emissions or renewable energy shares) are typically used to make statements about how different assumptions³ about the future may impact the development of these variables.

Assumptions about such futures are typically described by a scenario. The scenario is quantified by projecting the variables of interest while using a specific analytical setup, including one or more models. The projection process of the scenario includes pre-processing and the feeding of input data into a computational model, which conducts a model calculation and provides output data.

In this paper, we refer to important terms such as ‘scenario’ in the meaning as defined in the current version (1.12.0) of the Open Energy Ontology (OEO; for an introduction to the OEO see Booshehri et al. 2020)⁴. According to the OEO, for example, *a scenario is an information content entity that contains statements about a possible future development based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions and their motivation.*⁵

Variables of interest – endogenous data⁶ – are projected into the future, using a model⁷, conducting a model calculation⁸. Such a projection is accomplished based on the parameterisation⁹ of the model(s) used, reflecting the assumptions of the given scenario quantitatively. The data used for the parameterisation can be considered as exogenous data¹⁰.

¹ Öko-Institut e.V.; contact: h.foerster@oeko.de

² Otto von Guericke Universität Magdeburg; contact: mirjam.stappel@ovgu.de

³ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000063: An assumption is an information content entity about a property of a system or process. It determines a part of a scenario content.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2021.100074>

⁵ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000364

⁶ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00030030: Endogenous data is a data item whose quantity value is determined by a model.

⁷ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000274: A model is a generically dependent continuant that is used for computing an idealised reproduction of a system and its behaviours.

⁸ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000275: A model calculation is a process of solving mathematical equations of a model.

⁹ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00010260: Parameterisation is the process of translating assumptions into exogenous data the model can use.

¹⁰ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00030029: Exogenous data is a data item whose quantity value is determined outside of a model and is imposed on a model.

Scenario comparisons comprise a qualitative part, and scenario projection comparisons build on that and can include a quantitative part as well as a qualitative part.

We use the shorthand *SSPC* (*scenario and scenario projection comparison*) in the case that both parts are included in the comparison.

SSPCs are already regularly conducted to learn about specific areas of interest and inform policy making. These areas include, for example, viewing projections in hindsight when empirical data that was previously projected becomes available (EEA 2015)¹¹, comparing projected emissions pathways (O'Neill et al. 2016)¹², exploring economic adjustment costs to greenhouse gas emission reduction targets (Böhringer et al. 2021)¹³, exploring projected ranges of technological choices for mitigation (Dagnachew 2019)¹⁴, or assessing the consideration of sustainability aspects of scenarios (Child 2018)¹⁵.

Another example is the comparison of a baseline scenario with existing policies and measures to the effect of additional policies and measures on projected GHG emission reductions. Annex I Parties to UNFCCC provide such information as part of their National Communications and Biennial Reports (see also European Union 2017¹⁶).

Here, we aim to contribute to increasing the value of such comparisons. We draft elements of a typology which structures SSPCs according to a specific workflow and according to important elements that are currently, to our knowledge, not yet explicitly spelled out in the literature.

We believe that structuring and understanding the different elements of SSPCs can help in at least two areas:

- 1) Our draft typology helps to **understand already existing comparisons from the literature better** with respect to their characteristics and makes their added value more explicit.
- 2) Our typology **provides a systematic approach** to identifying scenario data that is sufficiently similar for SSPCs and shows the limitations that need to be considered when planning to apply metrics to data.

Our draft typology helps to classify comparisons. This, in turn, can help to connect related research and foster exchange. Our typology also serves as input for the development of the Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG) which will help explore scenarios and scenario projections on the Open Energy Platform (OEP) and support SSPCs on that platform.

Our paper is structured as follows:

In Section 2 we provide some insights into SSPCs from the literature and spell out our interpretation of the research questions addressed with the comparisons. In Section 3 we outline a general approach to SSPCs with the aim to lay out a standardised workflow. In Section 4 we introduce the elements of SSPCs and in Section 4.4 combine our findings into a draft typology of SSPCs.

Section 5 demonstrates how the approach to a SSPC and the building blocks are tied together by conducting case-studies with data available on the Open Energy Platform.

¹¹ https://www.eea.europa.eu/ds_resolveuid/e4ceb743705e455bbff83e6c11ca276f

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3461-2016>

¹³ <https://www.ifw-kiel.de/fileadmin/Dateiverwaltung/IfW->

[Publications/Sonja_Peterson/Climate_Policies_after_Paris_Pledge_Trade_and_Recycle/KWP_2183_EMF_overview_01.pdf](https://www.ifw-kiel.de/fileadmin/Dateiverwaltung/IfW-Publications/Sonja_Peterson/Climate_Policies_after_Paris_Pledge_Trade_and_Recycle/KWP_2183_EMF_overview_01.pdf)

¹⁴ Dagnachew, A., et al.; 2019; Insight into Energy Scenarios - A comparison of key transition indicators of 2 °C

Scenarios; https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2019-insight-into-energy-scenarios_3686.pdf

¹⁵ Child et.al. (2018): Sustainability guardrails for energy scenarios of the global energy transition. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S136403211830176X>

¹⁶ https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/459381_European%20Union-NC7-BR3-1-NC7%20BR3%20combined%20version.pdf

We conclude the paper in Section 6 providing an outlook and ideas for further research.

2 Examples from the literature

With some examples from existing comparison studies, we want to show in this section, that various types of SSPCs can be performed and different conclusions can be drawn from the comparisons.

For the collected examples, we extracted research questions, either directly given in the study report or derived from its description. Usually, we find a “general research question” that provides the overall context and which indicates the main goal of the study. Further, we may find several “specific research questions” in a study that focus on more detailed aspects for a particular comparison within the study and the scope of the general research question.

Some SSPCs focus on scenarios obtained with the **same modelling approach or by the same actor, but for different scenario definitions**. Here, the general research question might be to learn about how the different scenario characteristics impact results.

Another approach of SSPCs is comparing results where the **scenario definition is the same or harmonised** to yield insights into ranges of results projected by **different modelling approaches**. The model comparison projects of EMF¹⁷ are one such example.

However, several comparison studies in literature formulate goals or research question that are rather **independent from the model used or from a harmonised scenario definition**. By **allowing differences** here, they may concede less straightforward transparency for users/ readers and a straightforward interpretation, for the benefit of comparing other important aspects of the scenarios narrative / storyline. We have collected some examples with different research questions to show the variety of approaches. We derived the research questions from the methodology descriptions of the study reports.

Dagnachew (2019)¹⁸ compares scenario projections with the main focus on the following general research question: *What are the main similarities and differences between published 2 °C scenarios, focusing on the timing of emission reductions, the energy mix, and the scenarios' implicit and explicit reliance on technologies that remove CO₂ from the atmosphere?*

To answer this research question, several specific **quantitative comparisons** were made. For example: *How much do the following key indicators change in the investigated scenarios between 2017 and 2030? Key indicator were the CO₂ emissions from industry, buildings, transport and electricity generation, the final energy demand, the primary energy use of coal, oil, natural gas and renewables, the electricity generation from renewables, as well as the electricity use of transport, industry and buildings*. The study report depicts the results of the comparison in table 5.1, page 29. It uses a heat map that indicates by colours the relative speed of transition in the compared scenarios. It is a complex quantitative comparison including several parameters from six different scenarios and studies respectively.

Another example for a specific **quantitative research** question from Dagnachew (2019) is: *How does the global primary energy mix change between 2017 and 2030, between 2030 and 2040, and between 2040 and 2050 in the investigated scenarios?* Compared were coal, oil, natural gas, nuclear energy, bioenergy, hydro

¹⁷ <https://emf.stanford.edu/projects> <https://emf.stanford.edu/projects>

¹⁸ Dagnachew, A., et.al; 2019; Insight into Energy Scenarios - A comparison of key transition indicators of 2 °C Scenarios; https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2019-insight-into-energy-scenarios_3686.pdf

and other renewables. The quantitative comparison is shown in the study report in Figure 4.5 on page 23 and in three stacked bar plots, that indicate the change of the global primary energy mix in EJ per year.

For the comparison study of Deason (2018)¹⁹ we summed up the general research question as: *What are the main similarities and differences regarding flexibility and electricity generation cost of scenarios with 100% RE-share for various regions?* In this study, no specific scenario study is given.

The SSPC also **compares quantitative projection results**, which can be translated into more specific research questions, for example: *How does the technology mix of the variable generation capacities differ in the investigated scenarios, expressed in fractions of the total variable generation capacity by type of technology, i.e. solar pv, offshore wind, onshore wind, undefined wind and ocean?* The representation of this comparison is visible in Figure 4 in the report (page 3173 of the journal) as a stacked normalised bar plot, which shows for each scenario the share of the different variable generation capacities summed up to 100%. Further, it indicates the share of the total variable generation capacity on the total scenario generation capacity.

As another example for a SSPC, Child (2018)²⁰ investigates sustainability aspects in scenario studies. The general research question can be formulated as follows: *How are sustainability guardrails deployed in global target energy scenarios for the year 2050 in studies with high relevance?*

This study provides an example for specifically **comparing a qualitative aspect**, in this case regarding the scenario and scenario projection transparency: *How transparent (i.e. scientifically retraceable and reproducible) are the scenarios and their projections regarding scope, data sets, assumptions and modelling?* The results of the comparison are shown in Table 3, p. 330 of the journal. In a matrix, several aspects of transparency regarding the publication, i.e. general information, data, assumptions and modelling, of each scenario are indicated with a traffic light system: the color green signs “explicitly stated” information, yellow stands for “not fully disclosed” information, and red indicates information that is “not available / cannot be determined”.

In Tsiropoulos (2020)²¹ the general research question is explicitly stated as *the aim “[...] to identify the similar elements as well as diverging scenario results towards achieving at least 50% of GHG emission reduction by 2030 (compared with 1990) and near-zero emissions by mid-century in the EU28.”*

A quite complex specific comparison, which is shown in Figure 3 in the respective report, can be summarised as follows: *What is the increase of renewable energy sources, nuclear energy and CCS in the selected scenarios compared to 2017? What is the reduction in final energy consumption in 2050 compared to 2017? And what is the share of RES in final energy consumption in 2050?* It contains **qualitative and quantitative elements**: the compared studies are sorted into a 3 x 3 matrix and ordered by the reduction of final energy on the x-axis and the RES share in 2050 on the y-axis. For each study, the growth in renewable energy sources in gross inland consumption, the (de)growth in nuclear power generation and the amount of CSS in 2050 are indicated via traffic light colours, that symbolise a certain range in the values.

¹⁹ Deason, W. (IAEA); 2018; Comparison of 100% renewable energy system scenarios with a focus on flexibility and cost; Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.026>

²⁰ Child et.al. (2018): Sustainability guardrails for energy scenarios of the global energy transition. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S136403211830176X>

²¹ Tsiropoulos et.al. (2020): Insights from scenarios in line with the 2030 and 2050 ambitions of the European Green Deal. JRC Technical reports. doi:10.2760/081488

The study of Paltsev (2016)²² lays its general focus on normative aspects in view of validating scenario projection data in hindsight: *How can low-carbon goals in the latest projections be assessed? When and where can a set of energy scenarios offer useful information for decision-makers?* There, a bunch of recurring of scenario projections from several actors are compared with historic data (validation in hindsight).

One specific **quantitative research question** in this SSPC we derived as: *How do the projections on capacities of solar PV and CSP from 2015 until 2035 develop in IEA WEO scenarios between 2006 and 2014?* The results of the comparison are illustrated in figure 9 in the report, showing the cumulative capacities for each scenario over time. The scenarios are differentiated by colours, the real historic data is indicated by black dots.

These examples from literature show, that many research questions focus on numeric values, which we call quantitative comparisons. Comparisons, that focus on qualitative questions are also performed, of which only few are actually described as such or depicted in figures. The variety of the referred comparison studies suggest that neither the research questions (general and specific), nor the illustrations of the comparisons are limited.

3 General approach to scenario and scenario projection comparison (SSPC)

In this section, we describe the general process of comparing scenarios and their projections. We distinguish the comparing process into several parts.

- 1) Every SSPC is motivated by a research question. The selection of the scenarios to be compared depends on that research question.
- 2) Qualitative comparisons should be performed from a bird's eye view.
- 3) Some research questions require a quantitative comparison, based on numeric values from the scenario projection.

Every comparison should be checked against these observations, after which the results of the comparison can be visualised, analysed, and interpreted.

If we consider the literature, both qualitative and quantitative comparisons are performed in comparison studies (see Section 2). However, in most of the cases a distinction between the two types is not explicitly declared. Provocatively speaking: "Comparison" is often used as a general term and anyone implicitly knows, what it refers to.

Also, during our project work with an interdisciplinary team, we found, that there were different understandings of what a comparison was, even within the team. For some, the line-up of contents next to one another is understood as a comparison already, whereas others apply metrics to quantitative data (e.g. calculating maximum, minimum, averages, and differences) to make an explicit comparison.

With this paper, we aim to clarify the different types of comparison methods applied in the literature and to systematically describe the process of comparison (see also Figure 1). We want to point out that, when talking about energy and climate scenarios and their projections, both qualitative and quantitative comparisons are performed and justifiably so. Eventually, we would like to argue for a more precise differentiation when it comes to documenting the methodology in SSPC studies.

²² Paltsev, S., (2016): Energy Scenarios: The Value and Limits of Scenario Analysis; MIT CEEPR; WIREs Energy and Environment; <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.242>

Figure 1: Draft schema of the process of comparing scenarios and scenario projections

Source: own representation

3.1 Research question and scenario selection

An SSPC is usually initiated by a research question – Why are we doing this comparison? – to which the comparison can provide an answer. Even if the research question is not stated explicitly, it is fundamental for the purpose and the aim of an SSPC. An SSPC study may have several research questions, some rather general, others more specific.

The research question provides the context for a scenario (projection) comparison and guides through the comparison process. The research question can be very broad or very detailed or focused on a very specific detail. It can refer to a qualitative (scenario) or a quantitative (scenario projection) comparison. Eventually, it determines whether a comparison is reasonable or compares “apples vs oranges”.

Section 2 provides some examples for research questions from the literature.

Based on the research question, a set of criteria for scenario selection can be derived which may be found in any part of the scenario: assumptions, storyline / narrative, scenario type, scenario projection data or metadata. The criteria can refer, for example, to the scenario year or to the share of renewables. It can address the transparency and access conditions of projection data, i.e. which license it has or whether a license exists at all. Or it may refer to the authors of the scenario study or the models used. In other words, it can be very diverse.

Scenarios that meet these criteria qualify for being considered in the scenario comparison.

3.2 Qualitative scenario comparison (SC)

The qualitative comparison is the first type of comparison. It provides answers and insights to qualitative research questions that refer to structural or content-related topics of the scenarios. When conducting a

qualitative scenario comparison, the researcher discovers and analyses similarities and differences among the scenarios.

Examples for qualitative research questions are the following, assuming a researcher already has selected two or more scenarios he/she would like to compare qualitatively:

- Do the selected 100% renewable energy share scenarios also depict the transport sector? If yes, how detailed?
- (How much) Are the selected scenarios created with regard to open science criteria (e.g. Are the selected scenarios published under an open licence? Is the scenario data published according to the FAIR criteria?)
- At which level of detail do the selected scenarios consider spatial resolution?
- Do the selected scenarios consider Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technology?

The example questions above can be answered by analysing and comparing the s narratives / storylines, their assumptions and the metadata of the selected scenarios.

Qualitative scenario comparisons can either have the goal to answer a qualitative research question, or they can be used to investigate whether a quantitative comparison could be valid and significant enough to be conducted. Especially when scenario projection comparisons are performed that have different scenario definitions *and* modelling approaches (type *different-different*, see Section 4) are performed, a preceding qualitative scenario comparison provides answers on how “similar” the compared scenarios are, with respect to the research question.

Therefore, we suggest considering a qualitative comparison as a necessary first part of any comparison, even if the research question aims at a quantitative comparison.

3.3 Quantitative scenario projection comparison (SPC)

The quantitative SPC is the second, and optional, part of a comparison. It is about comparing quantitative data (numeric values) among the selected scenarios that were projected conducting a model calculation. It depends on the research questions whether it is applied or not.

For the quantitative SPC, we have to render the quantitative data from the selected scenario projections comparable, which we call *data alignment*. To do so, we must consider information from the datasets involved in projecting the scenarios and the scenario’s metadata. We first identify the respective datasets and their structure. Depending on the structure and content of the data sets, we may have to apply filters, i.e. select specific data items. Further, it is likely that we must perform transformations of any kind on the data to make them comparable. Such a transformation could, for example, be a unit conversion (e.g. kWh to MJ) or an aggregation of data to achieve coherence and comparability.

4 A draft typology for SSPCs: Elements and visualisation

Above we depicted how the parts of a process for SSPCs could look like. Here, we want to build on this and spell out important elements of such comparisons. Together, these elements should help understanding comparisons better (e.g. their value added, but also potential limitations) or enable to structure own comparisons. We derived three key elements, which we named **Information type**, **Aspects** and **Narrative-**

actor pairing and which we will elaborate on in the following. Together they make up our draft typology which we visualise and summarise in Section 4.4.

4.1 Information type considered

We distinguish between **qualitative and quantitative** information types.

A **qualitative scenario comparison (SC)** deals with comparing the characteristics of scenario narratives. It informs whether two or more scenarios are similar enough in their characteristics to allow for a meaningful quantitative scenario projection comparison or to interpret the differences.

Example 1: one scenario could be on Germany, the other on France, both consider total GHG emissions development from 2020 to 2050 in 5-year time steps. While the geographical scope is different, the variable of interest is the same and some quantitative comparisons may become meaningful. A researcher can then move forward to, for example, a quantitative scenario projection comparison (SPC) looking into the average yearly change in emissions between 2020 and 2050 for Germany and for France.

Example 2: one scenario is about Germany, the other about France. The scenario on Germany deals solely with projecting renewable energy shares from 2020 to 2030 in 5-year time steps. The scenario on France deals solely with projecting total GHG emissions from 2030 to 2050 in 10-year time steps. The characteristics of these scenarios may inform a researcher that while both scenarios deal with national level data, the further characteristics are not sufficiently similar as to allow for quantitative SPCs.

A **qualitative scenario projection comparison (SPC)** can help to gain insights about the similarity of approaches that were taken to project a scenario narrative into the future. It can include, for example information about the methodologies applied, the models used, the licensing information and so on.

Example: several scenarios covered in a study by Knopf et al. (2013)²³ were projected into the future using different modelling approaches. These included global general equilibrium models covering 1-25 European regions, global optimal growth models covering 1 and 2 European regions and partial equilibrium models of the energy sector covering 3-27(+3) regions in Europe. The different modelling approaches that were utilised on same scenarios can be part of the reasons why quantitative SPC results differ from one another. Such a qualitative SPC can thus help putting a quantitative SPC into perspective.

The **quantitative SPC** involves comparing quantitative data that is either input in or output of model calculations. The metric scale of the data limits the available operations that can be performed as part of the comparison:

- Nominal: data are shown next to one another, occurrences can be counted, the mode can be determined.
- Ordinal: data are shown in an ordered manner and ranking, a minimum, maximum and median can be determined.
- Interval: differences and mean can be calculated

²³ <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2010007813400010>

We provide three examples for scenario projection comparisons in Section 5. One calculates differences (Section 5.1) and the other displays data from three different scenario projections in one graph (Section 5.2). A third one depicts how data may need to be mapped to be made comparable (Section 5.3).

4.2 Aspects considered

SSPCs may cover different aspects.

Qualitative aspects of SSPCs usually cover information about the scenario's and scenario projection characteristics. These include:

Narrative/storyline: A narrative is a description of a possible future development, highlighting main scenario characteristics and dynamics, and the relationships between key driving forces²⁴. This includes the analysis scope²⁵ which describes the boundaries of what the scenario covers - e.g. study region²⁶ and time under scrutiny (scenario horizon²⁷). The narrative includes a documentation of assumptions in a qualitative way.

- Example: *a future world of very rapid economic growth, global population that peaks in mid-century and declines thereafter, and rapid introduction of new and more efficient technologies*²⁸.
- **Scenario projection methodology:** The methodology describes which tools and models were applied and parametrised to conduct a scenario projection.
 - Example excerpt: (...) *Auf Basis einer vollständigen Voraussicht wird dann im Rahmen einer linearen Optimierung der kostenminimale Einsatz von thermischen Kraftwerken, Stromspeisung aus erneuerbaren Energien, Pumpspeicherkraftwerken und flexiblen Stromverbrauchern unter Berücksichtigung technischer und energiewirtschaftlicher Nebenbedingungen bestimmt. Das Optimierungsproblem ist in GAMS implementiert und wird mit Hilfe des Simplex-Algorithmus gelöst. (...)* ²⁹
- **Metainformation:** Metainformation (metadata) is important information that further documents a scenario projection and its corresponding quantitative data. Ideally, metadata documents in a machine- and human-readable way the data sources used, contributors, nomenclature and license information. Thus, the metainformation may also inform qualitative comparisons by providing helpful context and inform interested persons transparently know about what they are allowed to do with the corresponding quantitative data originating from a scenario projection and under which constraints.
 - Example excerpt³⁰:

License	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Id: ODbL-1.0● Name: Open Data Commons Open Database License 1.0● Version: 1● Url: https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/● Instruction: You are free: To Share, To Create, To Adapt; As long as you: Attribute, Share-Alike, Keep open!● Copyright: © Reiner Lemoine Institut
----------------	--

²⁴ <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/> <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/>

²⁵ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020072 https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020072

²⁶ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020032 https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020032

²⁷ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020098 https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020098

²⁸ <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/> <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/>

²⁹ <https://www.oeko.de/oekodoc/2451/2015-608-de.pdf>

³⁰ Full metadata see: https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/abbb_simulation_parameter Full metadata see: https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/abbb_simulation_parameter

Quantitative aspects of SPCs relate to numerical data. According to the definitions in the OEO quantitative data relate to the inputs and outputs related to a model calculation which is applied to learn about what the narrative of a scenario would result in quantitatively when projected.

- **Inputs (exogenous data³¹):** Input data, program parameters³² and assumptions, are used for parametrising a model to match the scenario narrative. These parameters and assumptions are important drivers of model calculations and their specific characterisation has influence on the levels of the outputs.
 - Example: Energy prices are typical inputs to energy systems models and their value has influence on the level of demand of the corresponding energy carrier.
- **Outputs (endogenous data):** Outputs (output data³³) are the results of model calculations for projecting scenario narratives. Outputs express variables of interest using quantitative values.
 - Examples: GHG emissions in kilotons of CO₂-equivalent, renewable energy as share of gross final energy consumption, electricity generation by energy carrier in Terawatt-hours.

Quantitative SPCs can be conducted according to the scales (nominal, ordinal, interval) depicted above and additionally may be enhanced by further calculations to work out similarities and differences of the quantitative data in question.

4.3 Narrative-Actor pairing

Depending on the type of scenario, we suggest distinguishing different types of comparisons based on scenario-actor pairings that inform about the scenario narrative and the actors who projected the scenario (presumably with the same model). For our context, we think about an actor as a (research) institution³⁴ that conducts the scenario projection.

This pairing plays an important role for the qualitative comparison. It provides first insights on the expected level of similarity between scenarios and thus their level of comparability.

The results of a quantitative SPC based on data from two different actors and based on two scenarios whose narrative differ will need to be interpreted differently from results of a quantitative SPC where the scenario's narrative is equal (or very similar) and then projected by two different actors, applying different models for their model calculation.

To guide interpretability, we thus introduce the following classifications for comparisons:

- **same-narrative/same-actor (same-same):** A *same-same SPC* involves comparing scenario data from scenarios whose narrative are the same or very similar AND that are projected by the same actor. For example, detailed sectoral emissions for the scenario “with existing measures” (WEM scenario) are projected by all European Member States mandatorily every two years. The WEM scenario is defined

³¹ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00030029: Exogenous data is a data item whose quantity value is determined outside of a model and is imposed on a model.

³² https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000339: A program parameter is a variable that influences the output of a calculation in the program but has no meaning outside of the program

³³ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00020013: Output data is endogenous data that is determined by a model calculation and presented as a result

³⁴ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000238: An institution is an organisation that serves a social purpose

in Article 2 (9) Regulation (EU) 2018/1999³⁵. Assume, Member State X applies the same model³⁶ every two years to project this scenario. While the scenario is defined equally throughout the years, exogenous data to parametrise the model calculation may change as time passes and thus projection outputs may differ between the same actors WEM scenario projections submitted over the years. Conducting such a comparison may provide insights into the level of changes in the output data. We provide a short case-study for this scenario-actor pairing in Section 5.1

- **same-narrative/different-actor (same-different):** A *same-different SPC* involves comparing scenario data from scenarios whose storylines are the same or very similar AND that are projected by different actors. For example, model-intercomparison projects such as EMF-28³⁷ define a set of scenarios and their characteristics³⁸ that are then projected by different actors, using their respective modelling approaches. Results from a scenario projection can then be compared across the actors. Comparisons like this may provide valuable insights into potential ranges of results as a multitude of modelling approaches can be considered at the same time.
- **different-narrative/same-actor (different-same):** A *different-same SPC* involves comparing scenario data from scenarios whose storylines are different AND that are projected by the same actor (presumably with the same model). For example, the scenario “with additional measures” (WAM scenario) is projected by several European Member States every two years and submitted to the European Commission. This scenario is defined in Article 2 (10) Regulation (EU) 2018/1999³⁹. Assume, Member State X provided a WEM and WAM scenario projection in 2021. Conducting a comparison of the output data of the two scenario projections can provide insights into the level of changes that may be attributed to the different assumptions based on the different characteristics of the scenarios. In this specific case it may provide insights into how additional measures may contribute to changes in greenhouse gas emissions. We provide a short case-study for this scenario-actor pairing in Section 5.2.
- **different-narrative/different-actor (different-different):** A *different-different SPC* involves comparing scenario data from scenarios whose storylines are different AND that are projected by different agents.
We provide a short case-study in Section 5.3, but do not proceed with the quantitative comparison due to challenges of aligning the data.

A special case diverging from the above introduced pattern, and that we currently do not include in the typology is:

- **validation-in-hindsight:** A *validation-in-hindsight SPC* involves comparing scenario projection data with empirical data once the empirical data becomes available. Such a comparison can, for example,

³⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018R1999&from=EN#d1e1053-1-1><https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018R1999&from=EN#d1e1053-1-1>: ‘projections with measures’ means projections of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions by sources and removals by sinks that encompass the effects, in terms of greenhouse gas emission reductions or developments of the energy system, of policies and measures that have been adopted and implemented

³⁶ https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000274https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000274: A model is a generically dependent continuum that is used for computing an idealised reproduction of a system and its behaviours.

³⁷ <https://emf.stanford.edu/projects/emf-28-effects-technology-choices-eu-climate-policy> <https://emf.stanford.edu/projects/emf-28-effects-technology-choices-eu-climate-policy>

³⁸ Scenario definitions see <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2010007813400010> Table 1. Scenario definitions see <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2010007813400010> Table 1.

³⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018R1999&from=EN#d1e1053-1-1><https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018R1999&from=EN#d1e1053-1-1>: ‘projections with additional measures’ means projections of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions by sources and removals by sinks or developments of the energy system that encompass the effects, in terms of greenhouse gas emission reductions, of policies and measures which have been adopted and implemented to mitigate climate change or meet energy objectives, as well as policies and measures which are planned for that purpose

provide insights into whether scenario projection outputs converge towards the empirical data the closer the scenario projections are conducted to the year for which the empirical data becomes available. Such a comparison has been accomplished by EEA (2015).

4.4 Visualised draft typology for SSPCs

Considering the information from this section, we represent our draft typology as laid out in Figure 2, in general on the left and in specific on the right.

The narrative actor-pairing is depicted on the top as the element that steers. The more “same” in its combination, the more quantitative a comparison can likely be, as it can be expected that quantitative data will come about in comparable definitions (e.g. sector division, units) and require no or only little effort to be made comparable.

The more “different” we find in a narrative-actor-pairing the more qualitative / overarching a comparison will likely be, as we are less certain that data comes in comparable forms or can be made comparable by conversion.

The narrative-actor-pairing thus sets the general scene for a comparison and provides a first indicator on what will likely be possible and meaningful and what will not.

Having the narrative-actor pairing at hand, information types will be explored according to relevant aspects. Qualitative aspects cover details of scenario narratives, scenario projections methodologies and metadata and are considered in the first part of every comparison (see also workflow depicted in Figure 1). Quantitative aspects of scenario projections are then considered to explore input and output data of scenario projections during the second part of a comparison (see also Figure 1).

Figure 2

Source: own representation

5 Scenario projection comparison: Case studies on the Open Energy Platform

In this section we provide three short case-studies based on data that are currently available on the Open Energy Platform (OEP). These case-studies exemplify shortly, and for each building block of our draft typology how

a scenario projection comparison can be operationalised by human (and machine) users of the OEP, based on the approach we described in Section 3. We organise the case-studies according to the narrative-actor pairings documented under Section 4.3 and underline elements from the draft typology.

We need to mention, that at the current state of development of the OEP, a basic knowledge about the studies and scenarios which are published there is a precondition for comparing scenarios meaningfully. In the future, this knowledge will be stored in the OEKG and be accessible for all users on the OEP.

5.1 Same-same scenario projection comparison

The same-same scenario projection comparison involves comparing projected scenario data from scenarios that have the same characteristics and were projected by the same agent and model respectively. Such a comparison can happen, for example, when scenarios with the same characteristics are projected in a recurring manner, e.g. every two years as the WEM scenario is under EU-legislation as introduced in Section Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. A special case of a same-same comparison may also entail comparing data from different scenario years within the same scenario to learn about developments within the scenarios time-frame.

A specific and quantitative research question with a focus on outputs may be: *How do projected total GHG emissions in 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040 differ in the WEM scenario submitted by European Member States to the European Commission in 2019 from the WEM scenario submitted by European Member States to the European Commission in 2021.*

Part 1: qualitative comparison (information type): Identifying those scenarios in the OEP that include the type of data needed for quantitative comparisons is a necessary first, qualitative, step to proceed. In this case querying the OEP⁴⁰ for "EU-legislation" and "emission-projection", provides an overview of tables that may include the wanted information (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Some search results for "EU-legislation", "emission-projection" on the Open Energy Platform

Name	Tags
2014 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (eu_leg_data_2014_eio_ir_article23_t1)	EU SIROP emission-projection 2014 CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2015 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (eu_leg_data_2015_eio_ir_article23_t1)	EU SIROP emission-projection CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation 2015 Öko-Institut
2016 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation, quality checked by EEA (eu_leg_data_2016_eea)	EU SIROP emission-projection CC-BY-4.0 2016 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2016 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (eu_leg_data_2016_eio_ir_article23_t1)	EU SIROP emission-projection CC-BY-4.0 2016 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2017 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation, quality checked by EEA (eu_leg_data_2017_eea)	EU SIROP emission-projection 2017 CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2017 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (eu_leg_data_2017_eio_ir_article23_t1)	EU SIROP emission-projection 2017 CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2018 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation, quality checked by EEA (eu_leg_data_2018_eea)	2018 EU SIROP emission-projection CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation Öko-Institut
2018 greenhouse gas emission projections submitted by European Member States under the Monitoring Mechanism Regulation (eu_leg_data_2018_eio_ir_article23_t1)	2018 EU SIROP emission-projection CC-BY-4.0 EU-legislation Öko-Institut

Create Table
 in the model_draft schema.

Filters

How to work with Tags and Filter

Add Tags to a table:
 Tags can be added when viewing a table.

Create new Tags:
 You can create new Tags.

Find data resources:
 Use the Filters on Tags or try searching for strings that occur names. You can combine text and Tags filters to get more p you filter for multiple Tags, only tables containing all filtered displayed.

Tags

Source: own representation

⁴⁰ Direct queries on data tables via filters and tag under: <https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/schemas> Direct queries on data tables via filters and tag under: <https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/schemas>

Using the names and attached metadata, users can find out more. For example that there are two datasets for 2019: one, submitted originally by Member States, and another one that underwent quality assurance and control and gap-filling; this information is provided in the metadata displayed below the selected data table. For our case study we assume users are interested in the originally submitted data. They thus select the tables “eu_leg_data_2019_rep_table_1⁴¹” and “eu_leg_data_2019_eio_ir_article23_t1⁴²” for proceeding with step 2.

Part 2: quantitative comparison (aspects): Querying tables, either directly via API or after downloading (as csv / datapackage) two tables, can be included for the comparison. To approach the research question, the following filters need to be set for:

- country_code: all
- category: Total excluding LULUCF
- year: 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040
- gas: Total GHGs
- scenario: WEM

The differences between the total GHG emissions excluding LULUCF can then be calculated in percent. A negative value indicates that the WEM scenario submitted in 2021 exhibits for the given scenario year a smaller value than the WEM scenario submitted in 2019. While the scenarios are characterised by the same storyline – they include existing policies and measures – their parametrisation may have differed in 2021 compared to 2019.

⁴¹ https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/eu_leg_data_2021_rep_table_1

⁴² https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/eu_leg_data_2019_eio_ir_article23_t1

Table 1: Results of the same-same SPC with data available on the Open Energy Platform: Difference of projected total GHG in WEM scenario projections submitted by European Member States in 2019 and in 2021 in percent.

Country	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040
France	-13.6%	-9.8%	-11.9%	-12.8%	
Austria	-3.5%	-1.8%	-1.9%	-2.2%	-2.4%
Belgium	4.4%	3.2%	2.4%	0.4%	
Switzerland	-0.2%	-0.2%	-0.3%		
Cyprus	-3.5%	-14.6%	-14.6%	-12.6%	-11.5%
Czechia	0.8%	-2.2%	-2.2%	-2.9%	-11.7%
Germany	-11.5%	-6.2%	-13.3%	-26.3%	
Denmark					
Estonia	-37.5%	-27.8%	-14.6%	-21.2%	-26.7%
Spain	-5.4%	-1.2%	-3.8%	-4.7%	-4.0%
Finland	-5.1%	-5.7%	-11.4%	-13.2%	-15.8%
United Kingdom					
Greece	-3.5%	-1.8%	-3.0%	-3.6%	-3.9%
Croatia	0.0%	-2.0%	-3.8%	-8.3%	
Hungary	-1.9%	-2.9%	-5.4%		
Ireland	-7.0%	-2.4%	-10.0%	-1.5%	2.5%
Iceland					
Italy					
Lithuania	-2.2%	-7.2%	-11.6%	-12.0%	-12.8%
Latvia	-2.8%	-1.5%	2.5%	8.1%	-1.6%

+ Show 8 more

Source: own representation (available online: <https://datawrapper.dwcdn.net/nzxQU>) calculated from https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/eu_leg_data_2021_rep_table_1, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/eu_leg_data_2019_eio_ir_article23_t1

5.2 Different-same scenario projection comparison

The different-same scenario projection comparison involves comparing projected scenario data from scenarios that differ in their characteristics from one another and were projected by the same agent. Such comparisons may involve, for example, comparing less stringent with a more stringent greenhouse gas emissions scenarios.

A specific, and quantitative research question with a focus on outputs may be: *How do the projected total greenhouse gas emissions up to 2050 in Germany differ from each other in a business-as-usual scenario projection, compared to scenario projections with which target at emission reductions? The agent who projected these scenarios is the same.*

From the research question, we derive the following criteria:

- Projected GHG emissions
- Scenario year 2050
- Study region Germany
- Same agent

Part 1: qualitative comparison (information type): Identifying those scenarios in the OEP that include the type of data needed for quantitative comparisons is a necessary first, qualitative, step to proceed. In this case querying the OEP⁴³ for *greenhouse gas, germany, 2050*⁴⁴, provides an overview of tables that may include the wanted information (see Figure 4):

Figure 4: Some search results for “greenhouse gas”, “germany” and “2050” on the Open Energy Platform

Name	Tags
Projections of fugitive GHG emissions of scenario AMS2012 (ksz2050_r2_ams2012_fugitive_emissions)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut AMS2012 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Detailed data of GHG emission projections of scenario AMS2012 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ams2012_ghg_emissions_detailed_data)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut AMS2012 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Overview of GHG emission projections of scenario AMS2012 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ams2012_ghg_emissions_overview)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut AMS2012 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Projections of fugitive GHG emissions of scenario KS80 (ksz2050_r2_ks80_fugitive_emissions)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut KS80 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Detailed data of GHG emission projections of scenario KS80 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ks80_ghg_emissions_detailed_data)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut KS80 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Overview of GHG emission projections of scenario KS80 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ks80_ghg_emissions_overview)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung SzenarienDB 2030 Oke-Institut KS80 2050 Germany KSz-2050-R2
Projections of fugitive GHG emissions of scenario KS95 (ksz2050_r2_ks95_fugitive_emissions)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung 2030 SzenarienDB Oke-Institut 2050 Germany KS95 KSz-2050-R2
Detailed data of GHG emission projections of scenario KS95 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ks95_ghg_emissions_detailed_data)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung 2030 SzenarienDB Oke-Institut 2050 Germany KS95 KSz-2050-R2
Overview of GHG emission projections of scenario KS95 by gases and sectors (ksz2050_r2_ks95_ghg_emissions_overview)	2020 BMU Climate Protection Scenario 2050 Output-data 2040 Datenlizenz Deutschland -Namensnennung 2030 SzenarienDB Oke-Institut 2050 Germany KS95 KSz-2050-R2

Source: own representation

Using the attached metadata and linked study reports, users can find out more. For example, that there are three different scenarios (AMS2012 – a baseline, KS80 and KS95) with a 80 % and 95 % level of emission reductions respectively for 2050 compared to 1990. In a next step, a decision needs to be made which tables to use for the comparison and what kind of filters to apply.

Part 2: quantitative comparison (aspects): Querying tables either directly via API, or after downloading (as csv / datapackage) three tables can be included for the comparison⁴⁵. To approach the research question, the following filters need to be set for:

- variable: Emission
- year: 2020, 2030, 2040, 2050
- sector: Total (excl. LULUCF & international transport)
- greenhouse_gas: all

⁴³ Direct queries on data tables via filters and tag under: <https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/schemas>

⁴⁴ <https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario?query=greenhouse+gas%2C+2030>

⁴⁵ https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ams2012_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ks80_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ks95_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ams2012_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ks80_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ksz2050_r2_ks95_ghg_emissions_detailed_data

- unit: kt CO₂e

Users can then create the comparison shown in Figure 5 without making any further alignments or modifications to the data, except to divide the data by one thousand to better represent the units:

Figure 5: Results of the different-same scenario comparison with data available on the Open Energy Platform: Total German GHG emissions in three scenarios

Source: own representation (available online: <https://www.datawrapper.de/ /6k0fZ/>) based on https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ks2050_r2_ams2012_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ks2050_r2_ks80_ghg_emissions_detailed_data, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ks2050_r2_ks95_ghg_emissions_detailed_data

5.3 Different-different (scenario comparison)

Different-different comparisons consider projected scenario data that differ in their characteristics from one another and were projected by different agents, presumably using different models. Depending on the research question, whether qualitative or quantitative, the scenarios must have more or less aspects in common to allow for meaningful comparisons.

A specific, quantitative research question could be: “*How does the final energy consumption vary with respect to the energy carrier in scenarios with 80% reduction of GHG in the industry sector for Germany (or: in line with the Klimaziele der Bundesregierung) until 2050.*”

Deriving criteria which scenarios have to fulfil in order to be included in the comparison are:

- Projecting the scenario year 2050 and the study region *Germany*
- Projecting *GHG emissions*

- Modelling the *industry sector*
- Including *final energy consumption*, differentiated by *energy carrier*
- Be in line with the Klimaziele der Bundesregierung, which is *80% reduction of GHG emissions compared to 1990*

Part 1: qualitative comparison (information type): For the qualitative comparison on the OEP, the process can be initiated similarly to the one for case study 2, by querying the OEP for “greenhouse gas, germany, 2050” (see Figure 11). At the current state of the OEP, where scenario comparisons are possible only manually, it is recommended to take a closer look at the study reports to identify which additional criteria fit the scenarios to make an informed selection. In our case, we choose to compare the scenarios KS80 and DeVkopSys.

In a next step, a decision needs to be made which tables to use for the comparison and which kind of filters to apply. Data from two tables are evaluated. Both tables contain data on the final energy consumption, differentiated by energy carrier (see Figure 6). As we can see, both tables are structured differently, though, published in different languages and use different units of measurement. The conversion of the latter, however, is a solvable difference.

Yet, the scenarios group energy carriers differently, which is more complicated to address: KS80 classifies 8 categories (A#), whereas DevKopSys has 15 categories (B#), see Figure 7. Here, a mapping of the categories is proposed, indicated by colours and the code “M#”. However, the mapping is ambiguous. For example: the category “waste and other” (A5) from KS80 might be depicted in the DeVkopSys scenario (partially) within “Biogene Brennstoffe” (B1) and “Sonstige fossile” (B6). On the other hand, “Wasserstoff” (B13) from DevKopSys could be either mapped to “synthetic fuels” (A7) or to “fossil gases” (A5).

Such mapping problems are exemplary for the difficulties that researchers and stakeholders face when trying to compare scenarios. Comparing the scenarios qualitatively, we can identify such scenario-specific obstacles and assess whether a meaningful quantitative comparison is sensible.

Part 2: quantitative comparison: In this case study, more research on the scenario details would be necessary to really be able to compare the scenario data in a satisfactory way, e.g. by consulting the study reports or the researchers themselves. This step is beyond the scope of this paper.

Figure 6: Search results for final energy consumption

Source: own representation

Figure 7: Mapping of energy carriers in scenarios KS 80 and DeVkopSys

KS 80		Mapping	DeVkopSys	
Biofuels	A 1	M1	B 1	Biogene Brennstoffe
Lignite	A 2	M2	B 2	Kohle
Hard coal	A 3	M2	B 3	Diesel, Benzin
Mineral oil	A 4	M3	B 4	Heizöl
		M3	B 5	Kerosin
		M3	B 6	Sonstige fossil
Waste and other fossil_gases	A 5	M4	B 7	Erdgas
	A 5	M5	B 8	Liquefied Natural Gas
Solar_Geothermal and ambient heat	A 6	M6	B 9	Solarthermie
		M6	B 10	Umweltwärme
Synthetic fuels	A 7	M7	B 11	Power-to-Liquid
		M7	B 12	Synthetisches Methan
		M8	B 13	Wasserstoff
Electricity	A 8	M9	B 14	Strom
Derived heat	A 9	M10	B 15	Wärmenetze

Source: own representation based on https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/ks2050_r2_ks80_primary_and_final_energy_consumption, https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario/fh_iee_devkopsys_base_scenario_endenergie

6 Conclusion & further research/outlook

In this paper we have outlined relevant information for making scenario comparisons (SCs) and scenario projection comparisons (SPCs). We have developed a general workflow for such comparisons and discussed its elements. One important element of this is that to make a meaningful quantitative comparison, a qualitative comparison always needs to be accomplished first as it provides overall information on whether selected scenarios can be considered similar enough to proceed with quantitative SPCs.

Considering the overall workflow, we have established and described building blocks and outlined a draft typology for comparisons. This draft typology can help to identify - for existing scenario comparisons - what kind of comparisons were made. Knowing about different types of comparison helps to better understand the value added and limitations of existing scenario comparisons.

Our draft typology can also provide guidance for making and documenting scenario and scenario projection comparisons.

The Open Energy Platform (OEP) already provides a stock of scenario⁴⁶ and scenario projection⁴⁷ data on which several SPCs can be accomplished manually already. Our case-studies documented in Section 5 provide insights into how SPCs on the OEP can be accomplished based on the approach introduced in Section 3.

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG), which is currently under development⁴⁸, will include comparison functionality and will help to semi-automate some aspects of SSPCs directly on the OEP. It will also serve as the basis for the improved interface for factsheets including information on studies and scenarios.

⁴⁶ Scenario factsheets: <https://openenergy-platform.org/factsheets/scenarios/>. Please note, these will be updated to a better format in the future and be part of the RDF based study factsheets (<https://openenergy-platform.org/factsheets/rdf/study/>) currently under development.

⁴⁷ Scenario data: <https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/scenario>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oekg>

In our typology we implicitly assumed that when the same actor projects a scenario, this is accomplished by using the same modelling approach. While likely, this does not necessarily need be the case. For example, an actor may have more than one model at hand, or switch from using one to another over time. In addition, models evolve over time and therefore are subject to change. Different models might be used by various actors, e.g. when published openly. Future research may thus lead to extending our draft typology for taking into account the utilised model, too. In that case, the typology would be expressed in the following chain: narrative – actor – model. For the time being, we consider “same actor = same model” and within the limits of accuracy for SSPCs.

In this paper, we assume that researchers specify what to compare by a research question. From this question they derive criteria that scenarios have to accomplish for being similar enough to be compared. This approach takes into account that the question of similarity can only be fully answered with respect to a research question. Nevertheless, a general similarity of scenarios, that might be somehow measurable, might be of interest and, hence, focus of future research.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by grant 03EI1035A-D (SIROP) from the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK.IIC5).